

TRACE ELEMENTS DISTRIBUTION AND ENRICHMENT IN SOILS OVERLYING BARITES VEIN DEPOSITS IN THE PAYA DISTRICT, MIDDLE BENUE TROUGH, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The Paya Barites deposit typifies the numerous small (hidden) and uninvestigated barites mineralization that abound within the Benue Trough, Nigeria. Geological field studies and geochemical analysis of soils around the mineralized ridge was carried in order understand the general structural trend as well as assessing the trace elements distribution. Results of field geological investigations indicate Barites mineralization in vein systems, occurring as infillings in joints and fractures within an East – West trending ridge. Trace element geochemistry of soils overlying these veins revealed relative high values of Pb, Mn, Cu and Sr around the zone of mineralization. However, average Ba content of soils overlying the barites veins is similar in content to the regional background values indicating that the soils overlying the mineralized veins are not enriched in barium (Ba). Results obtained from this study have implications for pedogeochemical studies of blind barites deposits.

KEYWORDS: Soils, Barites, Veins, Geochemical Analysis, Trace Elements, Pedogeochemical

INTRODUCTION

The occurrence of barites ($BaSO_4$) in Nigeria was first reported by Tate (1959) revealing barites mineralization around Keana - Alosi, Akiri-Wuse, Shata/ Chiata / Ibi and Gbende-Gboko areas within the Middle Benue Trough with tentative reserves of about 40,000 tonnes. This report generated a lot of research interest over the years, all with the view of determining the structural orientation, geologic affinity and the ore content of such mineralization and their possible industrial application. Reserves of some of these deposits have been established and in some cases found to be economical, with the Azara deposits developed by the Nigerian Barite Mining and Processing Company, a subsidiary of the Nigerian Mining Corporation. The national gross production of this very essential raw materials is however, quite inadequate as compared to its high demand both locally and internationally. This therefore, necessitated a vigorous and detailed study of known barites deposits and the search for new ones in potential geologic environments of which the Benue Trough is known to be prolific (Turaki 1976; Ford 1981; Ogbeide 1981 and Chukwu 1994). These investigations and the mining of barites the world over have however, been restricted to exposed (known) and relatively large ore bodies with little attention paid to remote, concealed or hidden smaller occurrences which will be the saving grace for the future (Brobst 1979). It is in line with this, that a geochemical survey of soils overlying one of such smaller barites deposits is undertaken in order to understand the distribution of elements in the primary environment and the primary dispersion trend of such elements. This research is undertaken with the hope of collaborating, the findings of other researchers, most especially, the findings of Ogbeide, 1981, who undertook a reconnaissance survey around Azara area of the Middle Benue Trough aimed at detecting more barite veins and geochemical anomalies likely to be associated with barites mineralization. It is believed that trace element geochemistry remains the best approach in detecting and identifying such hidden small ore bodies or to a greater extent, delineating areas of possible alluvial barite occurrences.

Location and Physiography of the study area

The study area is located within sheet 212, south east of Shendam town, Plateau State. It lies between longitude $9^{\circ} 54' 48''$ E to $9^{\circ} 59' 55''$ E and latitude $8^{\circ} 34' 18''$ N to $8^{\circ} 42' 43''$ N. (fig.1). It is located about 45km south east of Mabudi in Langtang South Local Government Area. It can be assessed eastwards from the Langtang- Ibi highway at Yelwan - Shendam through Mabudi.

The Paya area is generally a low lying plain with the only upland being the mineralized barite ridge trending in an east-west direction. The ridge, which extends for about 1km, is approximately 2130feet (649.22m) high and less than 50m wide. Most part of the study area is covered by lateritic cap and overlain by thick layers of dark humus topsoil due to insitu weathering as a result of the flattish topography. The area gently slopes from Naki-Wase towards Gbaldum to Paya, but rises gently from Paya towards Yamani and south -east wards. The laterites at the mineralized zone (ridge) have been ferruginized but boulders of decomposed sandstones are however exposed through farming activities. It is intensely fractured, brecciated and eroded, exposing the sandstone beds and associated barite veins in the direction of the major W – E trend similar to the trend of other deposits within the Benue Trough (Offodile and Olayemi 1975; Turaki 1976 and Akponor 1993).

Geology

The Paya barites mineralization is found within the keana Sandstone, which is Cenomanian in age and overlying the Albian Arufu-Uomba- Gboko Formation, generally referred to as the Asu River Group within the middle Benue Trough (Obaje *et al* 1999), Keana Formation is a feldspathic sandstone that is believed to have originated from tectonically active province of granitic composition (Hoque *et al* 1984). However, the feldspathic composition decreases with increasing maturity of the depositional environment. The formation is a medium to coarse-grained sandstone, milky to gray in colour, poorly to well sorted and shows an increase in grain size and little intercalations of siltstones with depth. The zone enclosing the mineralized ridge is baked to (dark) gray colour. The presence of large phenocrysts within the barite crystals is indication that they are part of a later intrusion. Non barite-bearing sandstones are however, medium grained and light in colour.

The Paya barite veins occur at the crest of the ridge. Well-developed barite crystals are observed within the mineralized ridge, indicative of the presence of already existing fractures and bracciated zones to accommodate the intruded fluid of secondary geologic episode and allowed for the growth of such crystals. Mineralization at the surface, are in small veinlet systems (about 5cm) but tend to merge with depth thereby forming larger veins, they are exposed where eroded but generally covered by laterites which, in some locations have been ferruginized. The barite occurs as pure white crystal without any form of impurity, however, some samples were

observed to have phenocryst of surrounding country rocks. Unlike most other barite veins within the Benue Trough that occur in association with quartz (Ogbeide 1981), the Paya barite neither showed any appreciable quartz presence nor sulphide minerals which are commonly associated with barite mineralization (Chukwu 1994). Geochemical results however, indicate enrichment in elements associated with sulphide mineralization

Table 1. Trace Elements Distribution in Soils overlying Paya barite

Sample No.	Elements Content (ppm)						
	Zn	Pb	Mn	Co	Ba	Sr	Cu
SS1	13	87	570	30	40	28	14
SS2	72	525	870	20	550	320	40
SS3	41	228	1740	32	140	80	32
SS3B	32	224	370	13	108	60	17
SS3C	26	180	1160	28	94	51	22
SS4	38	98	420	12	206	106	48
SS5	10	70	100	22	45	28	24
SS6	42	38	1776	n.d	1230	140	20
SS7	24	80	900	n.d	40	12	38
SS7B	88	1460	2400	50	286	180	120
SS7C	84	3280	4880	12	156	53	138
SS8	4	27	180	5	14	9	6
SS9	26	54	480	n.d	16	6	4
SS10	4	n.d	48	n.d	25	15	3
SS11	32	53	878	n.d	50	31	24
SS12	6	38	45	n.d	25	12	3
SS12B	5	30	30	8	22	16	16

n.d = not detected

Geochemical Investigations

Early barite mineralizations were usually, mostly identified through surface geologic mapping due to the fact that they stand as distinct resistant ridges above the surrounding environment. They are known to be resistant to chemical weathering processes. Deposits cutting stream channels or rivers are also exposed but few deposits are however, flat, residual or even buried. Such veins are very difficult to identify and therefore requires some special techniques.

Geochemical exploration technique has been described as the best and the most successful for the identification of these blind deposits against the geophysical methods. In Nigeria, the only geophysical method used for the search of barite is the magnetic survey, using a portable Proton Magnetometer (Offodile 1977). The geochemical technique is achieved through sampling of stream sediments, soils, bedrocks or even vegetation. For good results and cost effectiveness soils and stream sampling are more applicable for reconnaissance survey. But due to the chemical inertness of barite to chemical weathering, its boulders are not likely to be transported very far from source and boulder tracing could prove to be a good method.

Sampling

Soil and rock samples were randomly collected to determine their petrography and trace element composition and distribution. Seventeen (17) soil samples were collected from pits of about 35cm deep and results obtained from analyses of these samples were used to assess the geochemical paragenesis, mineral assemblages, geochemical halos and the probable application of pedogeochemistry in the future search for barite through pathfinder elements that will be established

Analyses

Trace element analyses of the soil samples were carried out by instrumental method. 0.5g of the soil samples were weighed into 150ml glass beaker and 10ml of distilled water, concentrated hydrochloric, nitric acid and perchloric acid were added and boiled until white fumes were formed. 10ml of concentrated nitric acid and 50ml of distilled water were again added and heated for about 10 minutes before filtering into a volume and made up to 100ml after cooling. Each element was determined using the VGP Systems Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS), Model No.210 after setting the wavelength and Lamb Current of elements of interest along with their standards. Results obtained are given in table 1. These are compared with the result of reconnaissance survey of the Benue Trough (Ogbeide 1981) Table 2.

Table 2: Comparative Chemical content of soils around barite in Paya and other areas of the Benue Trough

Element	Conc. Range (ppm)		Mean (ppm)	
	1	2	1	2
Ba	25 – 1179	14 - 1230	177	180
Pb	10 – 44	27 – 3280	12	384.24
Zn	4 – 43	4 – 88		32.18
Cu	4 – 66	3 – 120	11	27.29
Mn	5 – 2400	30 – 4880	439	994.47
Sr	4 – 34	6 – 320	8	67.47
Co	n.d	5 – 50		14.29

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Included in Table 2 for comparison, is result the of a reconnaissance survey on sediments and soils around barite bearing zones within the Benue Trough (Ogbeide 1981). This gives an idea of the regional trace elements distribution in soils of the barite bearing zones of the Benue Trough (1) as compared with results obtained from the study area (2). Looking at the respective elements and relative abundance, it is seen that a strong relationship is established between the barite mineralization and some elements due to their relative abundance as compared with the regional values. Elements such as manganese (Mn), lead, copper, strontium and Zinc show relative abundance. This could be explained by the fact that the ionic radii of divalent barium (A1.43), allows it to be captured by the divalent ions of strontium; manganese oxides are also known to be very important carriers of Ba; copper – lead – zinc – iron oxides are gangues associated with barite mineralization and this association lay credence to barite being a low temperature hydrothermal ore (Ogezi and Akponor 1994)

Results show that Ba content ranges from 16ppm to 1230ppm. Ranges for other elements include Zn (4-88ppm), Pb (30-3280ppm), Mn (30-4880ppm), Co (5-50ppm), Sr (6-320ppm) and Cu (3-120ppm). Evaluation of the data revealed that soil samples no. 2, 3, 3B, 3C, 4, 7B and 7C are enriched in all the elements. Amongst these samples, nos. 3, 3B, 3C and 4 were collected directly at the top the ore- bearing vein, while samples 2 and 7B were collected near the mineralized ridge, except sample 7C collected within the alluvial sands north-east wards of the ridge. Contrarily, all other samples show low content of the assessed trace elements most especially, samples 8, 9, 10, 11, 12 and 12B collected at various distances away from the ore-bearing ridge. Of note are the discriminatory values of these elements in samples collected on the mineralized ridge and those in samples from adjoining sections. However, few samples from the mineralized ridge, such as sample 3B has relatively low Mn (370ppm), Cu (17ppm) and Co (13ppm) and sample 4 has low Co (12ppm).

As seen from tables 1 and 2, Zn concentration ranges from 4-88ppm with an average of 33.18ppm. The highest values of 72ppm, 84ppm, 88ppm were obtained from samples SS2, SS7B and SS7C. These and samples SS3, SS3B, SS3C and SS4 with relatively high values are from locations around the ore-bearing ridge (except 7C in the alluvial soils of River Wase). High concentrations of zinc around the mineralized ridge could be due to chemical leaching from the ore body. Lead and Manganese values ranged between 27-3280ppm and 30-4880ppm, averaging 384.24ppm and 994.47ppm respectively. These elements show the same trend of distribution but with average content far surpassing that of zinc. Their paragenesis and high level of susceptibility to weathering could be responsible for these concentrations because their sulphides are known to

have very close affinity for barium bearing minerals. Though, minerals such as ankerites and siderites were not identified on the field, they are known to always occur within barite veins; introducing oxidation effect on the mineralized veins and normally generating abundant oxides of iron and manganese. In the same manner, galena, though not identified, are known to be very common gangues of barite from where lead can be leached and enriched.

Cobalt (Co) content is generally low ranging from 5-50ppm (average of 14.29ppm), 50ppm was obtained from sample 7B, East of the ridge towards the alluvial soils, between Paya and Yamini, while sample 1 with 30ppm is north of the ore –bearing ridge, west ward of Gbaldum. Sample 3 (32ppm) and 3c (28ppm) is just within the ridge, while Strontium also showed affinity to the ore – bearing ridge as indicative of the high concentrations in samples ss2, ss7b, ss6, ss4 and ss3 with values of 320ppm, 180ppm, 140ppm, 106ppm and 80ppm respectively. With the exception of ss6 that is further down slope, all the other samples with high strontium values are located around the ore – bearing ridge, ss3B with 60ppm is on the ridge. Generally, the value ranges from 6-320ppm (67.47ppm). Likewise, Copper (Cu), ranged from 3-120ppm (average 27.29) and not showing any distinctive anomaly. Its average content around the mineralized ridge is however, generally higher. This is Similar to strontium, where ss7B, ss2, ss4 and ss3 are also enriched. There is a general enrichment of strontium in the local environment as compared to the regional values. Barium (Ba) has values of 14-1230ppm, averaging 180ppm. Ss3, ss3b, ss3c and ss4 sampled at the crest of the ridge gave Ba contents of 140ppm, 108.94ppm and 206ppm respectively. Again the sloppy area round the ridge, south to southeast wards as indicative of samples ss2, ss6 and ss7b are highly enriched, having values of 550ppm, 1230ppm, and 286ppm respectively. Generally, Ba has close values for both local and regional enrichment. The average Ba content in soils overlying the barite veins is about 180ppm. This compares favourably with the average regional background value of 177ppm (Ogbeide 1981). The chemical inertness of barite may be responsible for this lack of anomalous enrichment, even around the ore veins. This is however, in contrast with the findings of Ogezi and Aponor (1994) who opined that the low temperature hydrothermal fluids (source of barite mineralization) were more concentrated in trace elements and light earth elements, especially the incompatible elements-Ba, Sr and K. Assessment of the relative abundance of the elements reveal a strong relationship between the barite mineralization in Paya area and the concentration of Sr, Pb, Zn, Cu and Mn. Table 3 illustrates the trace element enrichment by samples and this can be correlated with the enclose geological map of the study area.

Table 3. Subdivision of the samples according to their level of enrichment

Element	Concentration values (ppm)			Samples with low concentr.	Samples with high concentration
	Low	Average	High		
Zn	4,5,6,10,13	24,26	32-88	1,3c,5,7,8,9, 10,12, 12b	2,3,3b,4,6,7b,7c,11
Pb	27, 30, 38	53, 54, 70	87-3280	5,6,7,9,10,11,12,12b	1,2,3,3b,3c,4,7b,7c
Mn	30, 45, 48	100-570	870-4880	1,3b,4,5,8,9,10,12,12b	2,3,3c,6,7,7b,7c,11
Co	5, 8	12, 13	20-50	1,3b,4,5,8,9,10,12,12b	2,3,3c,6,7,7b,7c,11
Sr	6-16	28-31	51-320	1,5,7,8,9,10,11,12,12b	2,3,3b,3c,4,6,7b,7c
Cu	3-17	20-24	32-120	1,3b,3c,5,6,8,9,10,11,12,12b	2,3,4,7,7b,7c
Ba	14-25	40-94	108-1230	1,3c,5,7,8,9,10,11,12,12b	2,3,3b,4,6,7b,7c

CONCLUSION

From the field and geochemical investigations, it can convincingly be concluded that the barite mineralization has a very high affinity for elements such as Mn, Pb, Zn, Sr and Cu. This is demonstrated by their relative high concentration at the local environment than the regional values. It is believed that these anomalies are related to the mineral paragenesis and topography of the area – being flat lying, the leached elements are not widely dispersed. This may also account for the restriction of the anomalous values around the mineralized ridge as indicated by the enrichments in samples ss2, ss6, ss7b and ss3. High trace elements concentrations are restricted to the mineralized ridge and areas eastwards, towards Yamini and surrounded by the alluvial soils of the two

major rivers, River Kwazu, River Pai and River Wase. Locations of ss8, across River kwazu, on the southern portion, ss5, 11, 12 and 12b at the far northern and northeastern parts did not show any appreciable enrichment. Ba showed no significant re-concentration in soils overlying the barite veins in the study area. Its value was similar to background values indicating that it was not enriched in soils overlying the mineralized veins. This may imply that Ba may not be too significant an element in pedogeochemical studies for blind (buried) and or alluvial barite deposits. This finding also, does not support the submissions of (Chukwu 1994) who recorded high Ba - Pb anomaly dispersion through geochemical stream sediments and residual soil profile studies in the Arufu – Akwana areas. Manganese (Mn), lead (Pb), copper (Cu), strontium (Sr) and zinc (Zn) could however, serve as good pathfinder elements for this purpose.

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